

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

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Leaderful Classroom Pedagogy Through a Multidisciplinary Lens: Merging Theory with Practice

Editors:

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Background

Revisiting our leadership identity each time before we walk into a classroom can give us an opportunity to re-examine what leadership tenets we demonstrate in the classroom and to what extent our leadership practices foster or limit our students' growth. Leadership identity development is an ongoing and dynamic process and evolves through reflective practice. When teachers are involved with self-examination and reflection, they can access their underlying values, beliefs, and assumptions about language education. Through this introspective process, teachers can recognize their own limitations and biases, and the privileged position they are granted in the classroom. As a result, they can develop an empathetic lens that will not only help them understand the challenges students are facing, but also, stimulate their desire to collaborate with them. We believe that collaborative leadership between the unequally positioned teacher and students originates from this empathetic lens.

Hence, this volume will shed light on how teachers' leadership identity transforms their pedagogical decisions and proposes a new framework, *leaderful classroom practices* which emerges through collaborative interactions between the teacher and students.

The pedagogical framework entails the following steps:

- Creating a psychologically safe learning environment by eliminating the preconceived power distance between the teacher and learners.
- Sharing power with learners by giving them a voice in pedagogical decisions.
- Encouraging learners for introspection to to unlock their full potential.

The multidisciplinary aspect of this volume should appeal to a wide range of readers from different fields and give them the opportunity to take a moment and reflect on their leadership identity, recognize the limitations of their practices, and adopt a leaderful classroom pedagogy in their respective disciplines.

We believe that establishing an open, democratic, and participatory learning environment for all learners is a major leadership responsibility of teachers, and this volume intends to demonstrate how to accomplish this mission both in theory and practice.

This call for proposals invites contributions across all disciplines with an emphasis on one or more of the following concepts:

- Teachers' leadership identity and how it impacts their pedagogical and class management decisions
- Application of leaderful classroom pedagogy (All disciplines)
- Application of collaborative leadership practices in the classroom
- Collaborative teaching and learning in the classroom
- Engaging learners in leadership roles in and outside the classroom
- Learners' perceptions of teachers' leadership identity and its influence on their learning

Guidelines for contributions

Please include the following in your proposals:

1. The tentative title and subtitle of your chapter
2. Name of author/s: Further details such as Affiliations of author/all authors, full physical address of all authors (required by the publisher), email addresses of all authors. Please also indicate the corresponding author by *, short bios of all authors, no more than ten lines per author. Please write as continuous text using the third person.
3. Your proposal should be approximately **500 words** including the background/context of your study, its aims, and relation to the pedagogical framework *leaderful classroom practices*, which is central to this volume, methodology, a summary of your findings, and keywords (5-8 words). Your complete manuscript should be no longer than **5000 words**.

Springer Nature demands that all manuscripts be based on empirical research findings. Due to the inclusive nature of this volume, contributions across all disciplines are strongly encouraged. If your abstract is accepted, you will also be asked to participate in the peer-review process to enhance the quality of the volume.

Please submit your proposals by using the following link:

<https://forms.gle/PMYncX9YPduMqu4v6>

Important Dates

July 15 - August 31, 2022: Call for Chapters

August 31, 2022: Deadline for proposal submission (Please see the submission guidelines).

September 15, 2022: Contributing authors will be announced. The number of accepted proposals will be determined depending on the quality of the submissions.

September 15 - December 15: Period to complete the first draft of full chapters.

December 15, 2022: Submission deadline for the first drafts.

January 15 - February 15, 2023: Revising your chapters.

February 15, 2023: Deadline for revised chapter submission (no longer than 5000 words).

February 15 - April 1, 2023: Final blind peer review.

May 31-June 31, 2023: Expected publication date.

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